

Effect of calcium on the uptake of cadmium by coriander (*Coriandrum sativum* L.)

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Manuscript received online 08 August 2013, accepted 06 April 2014

Abstract : A pot experiment was conducted to find out the effect of calcium on the uptake of cadmium by coriander (*Coriandrum sativum* L.) on the alluvial soil of Sheila Dhar Institute Experimental Farm, Allahabad. Three levels of calcium (0%, 1% and 2%) and Cd (0 mg kg⁻¹, 5 mg kg⁻¹ and 15 mg kg⁻¹) were applied as CaCO₃ and CdCl₂, respectively. Addition of 2% calcium increased the maximum dry biomass yield of coriander by 32.1% compared the control. The application of 15 mg kg⁻¹ Cd maximum reduces dry biomass yield of coriander by 22.2% compared the control and registered the highest accumulation of Cd in shoot of coriander by 4.3 mg kg⁻¹ over the control. Therefore, 2% calcium application may be recommended to enhance biomass yield of coriander.

Keywords : Cadmium, calcium, coriander, uptake.

Introduction

Cadmium (Cd) levels in arable land have increased during the last century due to anthropogenic activities. Most of the Cd transferred to humans comes from food, especially plant food. Carrots are of particular concern due to a large consumption of this vegetable. In the body, Cd is stored and may disturb essential functions and cause diseases and organ failure¹.

According to estimations 3 to 5% of the Cd in the food is absorbed during digestion². In the body the absorbed Cd is bound to a protein (metallothionein) in the liver. Some of these complexes reach to the kidney where Cd is accumulated in the kidney cortex³. The highest concentration in the liver is reached at an age of 20 to 25 and in the kidney between 50 and 60. After that, the concentration slightly decreases².

The biological half life of Cd is very long, ranging from 10–30 years². In the kidney, Cd causes damages on tubular cells and a level of 200 µg/g cortex is considered a critical level. Exceeding this concentration will cause irreversible damages and eventually lead to kidney failure. The damage of kidney cells will also affect the calcium and phosphorus metabolism, which increases the risk for kidney stone and Osteogenesis Imperfecta (brittle-

bone disease). That was what happened in Japan in the 1960s where, mostly women, who ate rice grown close to a mining company, got the itai-itai disease³.

Application of calcium carbonate – containing amendment significantly decreased the solubility of heavy metals in contaminated soils^{4,5} and increased soil pH, and all these combined to decrease the metal uptake by rice, wheat, and cabbage⁶. Many reports indicated that sulfur-containing amendments and organic-waste application to contaminated soils lowered the concentration of soluble Cd and Pb in soils⁷. To limit the intake of Cd by food, plant uptake is a good starting point. Soil properties and the cultivating measures greatly influence the Cd uptake by plants and are therefore of great concern. Liming has been suggested as a way to decrease plant Cd uptake but the results are inconsistent¹. The objectives of this study were to examine the effect of calcium on the uptake of Cd and the effects on their respective concentration in roots and shoots of coriander.

Results and discussion

Effect of Cd and Ca on dry biomass yield of coriander :

The data presented in the Table 1 indicated that the individual application of Ca 2% registered the increased

Table 1. Effect of Cd and Ca on dry biomass yield of coriander (g pot⁻¹)

Cd-rate (mg kg ⁻¹)	Ca-rate in %	Dry biomass yield (g pot ⁻¹)
0	0	20.24
0	1	22.56
0	2	26.74
5	0	18.75
5	1	21.65
5	2	22.18
15	0	15.75
15	1	16.72
15	2	17.26
SE		0.16
CD		0.33

Table 2. Effect of applied Cd and Ca on Cd concentration (mg kg⁻¹) in coriander roots and shoots

Cd-rate (mg kg ⁻¹)	Ca-rate in %	Cd concentration (mg kg ⁻¹)	
		Root	Shoot
0	0	0.24	0.20
0	1	0.21	0.17
0	2	0.16	0.13
5	0	1.76	1.26
5	1	0.95	0.55
5	2	0.22	0.18
15	0	6.86	4.30
15	1	2.35	1.65
15	2	0.46	0.26
SE		0.15	0.14
CD		0.31	0.29

maximum dry biomass yield of coriander by 32.11% (26.74 g pot⁻¹) over the control. The application of Cd @ 15 mg kg⁻¹ treated pot registered the maximum reduction in dry biomass yield 15.75 g pot⁻¹ (22.2%) of coriander either the control pots. Application of Ca boosted the dry biomass yield of coriander plants and was found to have ameliorative role in Cd contaminated pots. The combined application of Ca at the rate of 2% and Cd at the rate of 5 mg kg⁻¹ increased dry biomass yield 9.58% (22.18 g pot⁻¹) coriander compared the control pot. Effect of Cd toxicity on coriander was apparent from visual symptoms after 30 days of sowing. These symptoms were exhibited in the form of light white yellow spots on the lower leaves. The hazardous effect of Cd was observed minimized in Ca-treated pots, which might be also due to the ameliorative role of Ca in the physiology of plants. The similar results were obtained by Mani *et al.*⁸⁻¹⁰.

Clarkson and Lutge¹¹ reported that Cd damages the bio-membrane and cause enzymatic changes and possible interaction with macro and micro-elements leads to the phytotoxicity of this element. The decrease in yield with increasing rates of Cd application was also reported by Sarkunan¹² in rice; Georgieva¹³ in radish, pea and peeper; Ozturk¹⁴ in wheat.

Effects of applied Cd and Ca on Cd concentration (mg kg⁻¹) in coriander root :

The data presented in the Table 2 and graphically presented in the Fig. 1 indicated highly significant effect of Cd and Ca interaction of Cd × Ca on Cd uptake by

Fig. 1. Effects of applied Cd and Ca on Cd concentration (mg kg⁻¹) in coriander root.

roots of coriander plants. The individual application of Cd @ 15 mg kg⁻¹ registered the maximum (6.86 mg kg⁻¹) uptake of Cd for coriander roots. The study reveals that Cd, Ca and Cd × Ca interaction have influenced the uptake of Cd in root plants significantly even at 1% level of significance. Cd individually enhanced the Cd uptake by 0.24 mg kg⁻¹ to 6.86 mg kg⁻¹ respectively higher over the control in coriander as the doses of Cd increased from 0 to 15 mg kg⁻¹ respectively. But application of Ca @ 2% and Cd @ 5 mg kg⁻¹ competitively reduced the Cd concentration below 0.22 mg kg⁻¹ respectively in coriander roots and was found to have ameliorative role in Cd contaminated pots. Several reasons for Ca alleviation of

mineral toxicity have been considered. A proposed mechanism is the displacement of cell-surface toxic cations by Ca. Since plasma membrane surface are usually negatively charged, high level Ca^{2+} would reduce cell-surface negativity and alleviate the harmfulness of cationic toxicants¹⁵. It may be concluded that addition of liming substance (CaCO_3) would arrest the transfer of heavy metal (Cd) from plant to soil. Almost similar results have been reported by Rattan *et al.*¹⁶.

Application of adequate quantity of Ca prevents any shift in soil pH. Furthermore, the study also indicated that Cd adsorption was observed strongly pH dependent. The solubility of CdCO_3 and $\text{Cd}(\text{OH})_2$ is very low in neutral to alkaline range of the experimental pot. This may be ascribed due to the substitution of H^+ , Cd^{2+} and Fe^{2+} etc. like ions by ionic strength of Ca^{2+} . The result has been corroborated by the findings of Gomes *et al.*^{17,18}. Choi *et al.*¹⁹ showed that plant Cd tolerance in tobacco plants was increased by Ca application due to formation of Cd-Ca-containing crystals, and removal of these crystals through the head cells of trichomes. Suzuki *et al.*²⁰ investigated the effect of Cd toxicity on root growth inhibition in *Arabidopsis* seedlings supplemented with Ca. Retardation of root growth was observed, increasing cell death at growing points (root tips). On the other hand, application of Ca alleviates root growth inhibition due to a decrease in cell death.

Several mechanisms have been proposed to explain the effect of Ca on the alleviation of Cd toxicity. This may be due to the fact that the plasma membrane surface is usually negatively charged and a high concentration of Ca^{2+} would neutralize the membrane surface and minimize the toxic effect of Cd. It may also be due to the high concentration of Ca^{2+} around Ca channels which may decrease the influx of Cd^{2+} .

Effects of applied Cd and Ca on Cd concentration (mg kg^{-1}) in coriander shoot :

The data given in Table 2 and graphically presented in Fig. 2 indicated that as the levels of cadmium addition increased, the Cd uptake in the crops significantly increased. Cd individually enhanced the Cd uptake by 0.20 mg kg^{-1} to 4.30 mg kg^{-1} , respectively higher or more over the control in coriander as the doses of Cd increased from 0 to 15 mg kg^{-1} respectively. The individual appli-

Fig. 2. Effects of applied Cd and Ca on Cd concentration (mg kg^{-1}) in coriander shoot.

cation of Ca @ 2% registered the minimum concentration of Cd 0.13 mg kg^{-1} for coriander shoot. The application of @ 15 mg kg^{-1} Cd registered the maximum concentration of Cd 4.30 mg kg^{-1} for coriander shoot. But application of Ca @ 2% and Cd @ 15 mg kg^{-1} competitively reduced the Cd concentration below 0.26 mg kg^{-1} respectively in coriander shoots and was found to have ameliorative role in Cd contaminated pots. Almost similar results have been reported by Mani *et al.*^{8,22,16}.

Suzuki *et al.*²⁰ reported that Ca reduced the uptake and toxic effects of Cd in *Arabidopsis*. In tobacco, Cd tolerance was increased in the presence of Ca, probably due to the active exclusion of toxic Cd by the formation and excretion of Cd/Ca containing crystals through the head cells of trichomes¹⁹. It was also previously reported that the accumulation of Cd on seed germination of radish is reduced by high concentration of calcium²³.

Material and methods :

Experimental site :

The experimental site is situated at northern India at 25°57' N latitude and 81°50' E longitude on south-east facing slopes of comparable inclination at altitudes between 200 and 80 m above sea level. A sandy clay loam, derived from Indo-Gangetic alluvial soils of SDI farm situated on the confluence of Ganga and Yamuna alluvial deposit, was sampled from Allahabad city, India. The properties of the soil were : pH 7.8, EC 0.28 dSm^{-1} , organic C ($\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$ oxidation) 0.56%, total N 0.07%,

total P 0.038%, CEC 19.6 C mol (P⁺) kg⁻¹, DTPA-Cd 0.16 mg kg⁻¹. The texture was sand (>0.2 mm) 55.54%, silt (0.002–0.2 mm) 20.32% and clay (<0.002 mm) 24.25%. The detailed physicochemical properties of the investigated soil have been given in the Table 3. The soil was ground to pass through a 2 mm sieve. Plastic pots of a 5 liter capacity (each containing 5 kg of soil) were used. Fertilizers added per kg soil were 0.8 g calcium ammonium nitrate, 0.5 g di-ammonium phosphate and 0.367 g potassium sulphate. The experiment was replicated thrice and conducted in completely randomized block design following nine treatments as follows :

A pot experiment was conducted to test the hypothesis. Five kg soil was taken in each earthen pot. Total 27 earthen pots (having 9 treatments replicated thrice) were installed in an open natural light condition. The treatment combinations were as follow : T₁ control; T₂ Cd 0 mg kg⁻¹ + Ca 1%; T₃ Cd 0 mg kg⁻¹ + Ca 2%; T₄ Cd 5 mg kg⁻¹ + Ca 0%; T₅ Cd 5 mg kg⁻¹ + Ca 1%; T₆ Cd 5 mg kg⁻¹ + Ca 2%; T₇ Cd 15 mg kg⁻¹ + Ca 0%; T₈ Cd 15 mg kg⁻¹ + Ca 1%; T₉ Cd 15 mg kg⁻¹ + Ca 2%.

Ca was applied as CaCO₃ to provide Ca at the rate of 0, 1 and 2%. Cd was applied as CdCl₂ at the rate of 0, 5 and 15 mg kg⁻¹ of soil with three replications of each treatment. Soil in each pot was mixed thoroughly to ensure intimate distribution of applied Cd and Ca. After 24 h of the treatments, seeds were sown. Soil moisture was maintained by irrigating the crops at intervals of 5–6 days. Coriander was grown as a test crop.

Soil analysis :

Soil sampling :

For surface soil sampling, the larger fields were di-

vided into suitable and uniform parts, and each of these uniform parts was considered a separate sampling unit. In each sampling unit, soil samples were drawn from several spots in a zigzag pattern, leaving about 2 m area along the field margins. Silt and clay were separated by Pipette method and fine sand by decantation.

Extraction for total heavy metals content in soil :

One gram of soil in 5 ml concentration HNO₃ and 5 ml HClO₄ (perchloric acid 60%) were added and the contents were heated up to dryness. The hot distilled water was added. The contents filtrated and volume was made up to 50 ml. The clean filtrate was used for the estimation of Cd by AAS (Model Perkin-Elmer, Analyst600).

Preparation of DTPA solution :

Di-ethyl-tri-amine-penta-acetic acid (DTPA) solution {1.97 g (0.05 M) DTPA powder, 13.3 ml (0.1 M) tri-ethanol amine and 1.47 g (0.01 M) CaCl₂ were dissolved in distilled water made up to 1 liter after adjusting the pH to 7.3} was prepared²⁴ to extract the available Cd in soil samples.

Available heavy metals in soil :

Five gram soil and 20 ml DTPA solution was added and the contents were shaken for 2 h and then filtered through Whatman filter paper No. 42. The clean filtrate was used for the estimation of Cd by AAS (Model Perkin-Elmer, Analyst600).

Soil pH :

Soil pH was measured with 1 : 2.5 soil water ratio using ELICO pH meter (Model LI 127). Double distilled water was used for the preparation of all solutions.

Organic carbon :

One gram soil (0.5 mm) was taken in a 500 ml conical flask. Then 10 ml of 1 N potassium dichromate (K₂Cr₂O₇) solution and 20 ml of concentrated sulphuric acid (H₂SO₄) were added. The solution was shaken well for two minutes and kept for half an hour and then diluted with 200 ml of distilled water. Then 10 ml of phosphoric acid and 1 ml of diphenylamine indicator were added in solution. Then solution becomes deep violet in colour and further it was titrated against N/2 ferrous ammonium sulphate solution, till the violet colour changed to purple and finally to green. Organic carbon was determined by chromic acid digestion method²⁵.

Table 3. Physicochemical properties of soil on the Sheila Dhar Institute (SDI) Experimental Farm, Allahabad, India

Parameters	Values
Texture : Sandy Clay Loam (Sand, Silt and Clay %)	(55.54 ± 1.03, 20.32 ± 0.34 and 24.25 ± 0.36, respectively)
pH	7.8 ± 0.2
EC (dSm ⁻¹) at 25 °C	0.28 ± 0.03
Organic carbon (%)	0.56 ± 0.15
CEC [C mol (p ⁺) kg ⁻¹]	19.6 ± 0.6
Total nitrogen (%)	0.07 ± 0.02
Total phosphate (%)	0.038 ± 0.01
DTPA-extractable Cd (mg kg ⁻¹)	0.16 ± 0.06

Cation exchange capacity :

CEC was determined by using neutral 1 N ammonium acetate solution. A known weight of soil (5 g) was shaken with 25 ml of neutral ammonium acetate solution for 5 min and filtered through Whatman filter paper No. 42²⁶.

Total nitrogen :

A known weighed soil (1 g) was taken in a 150 ml conical flask and treated with 10 ml of digestion mixture containing sulphuric acid and selenium dioxide. Salicylic acid was also added to include the nitrates and nitrites. Digestion was carried out till the soil colour changed to white. The N in the digest was estimation by using micro-Kjeldahl method²⁶.

Total phosphorus :

Two gram soil was taken with 4 ml HClO₄ (70%) in a 50 ml beaker covered with watch glass and put on a hot plate and digestion was carried out till the soil colour changes to white. Ten ml HNO₃ was added to the filtrate solution. Ammonia was added to saturate the solution. Then 30 ml standard ammonium molybdate solution was added in the solution to extract the total phosphorus content from soil²⁶.

Plant analysis :

Processing plant samples :

Plants were harvested after 45 days. The fresh samples first washed with tap water followed by 0.2% detergent solution, 0.1 N HCl and then with a plenty of water. Final rinsing was done with distilled water. The samples were rinsed with double distilled water. Samples so cleaned and freed from dirt or other adhered contaminants were then soaked with tissue paper, and air-dried for 2–3 days in a dust and contamination-free environment. Thereafter the samples were placed in clean paper envelopes and dried in a hot-air oven at a temperature of 65 °C.

Preparation of plant extract :

One gram of ground plant material was taken in a 100 ml beaker and 15 ml of tri-acid mixture (HNO₃, conc. H₂SO₄ and HClO₄ in 5 : 1 : 1 ratio) was added. The content was heated on hot plate at low heat (60 °C) for 30 min and the volume was reduced to about 5 ml until a transparent solution was obtained. After cooling, 20 ml distilled water was added to the beaker and the content was filtered through Whatman filter paper No. 42 into a

100 ml volumetric flask and the volume was made up with distilled water²⁷.

Determination of heavy metals in plant :

Plant extract was used for the determination of Cd by Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer (Model Perkin-Elmer, Analyst600) at National Botanical Research Institute, Lucknow, India.

Statistical analysis :

Data were analyzed by factorial analysis of variation (ANOVA) using various treatments as independent factors with the help of the sum of square (SS) and degree of freedom (DF). The standard error (SE) is given by

$$SE = \sqrt{\frac{2V_E}{n}}$$
, where, V_E is the variance due to the error,

n is the number of replications, and the critical difference (CD) is given by $CD = SE_{diff.} \times t_{5\%}$ ($t_{5\%} = 2.042$ at $DF_{error} = 30$ was observed) and standard deviation (SD) were determined in accordance with²⁸.

Conclusion

The application of calcium to the soil possibly reduces cadmium in the edible parts of the plants and helps to reduce the risk to the health of people living in metal contaminated areas. In order to reduce risks, plants with lower accumulative nature should be growth for which further species and varietal screening should be done. A more detailed study is required to grow coriander or other vegetable crops in metal-contaminated areas and evaluate their growth and uptake of heavy metals in different edible parts of plants. There is a report that uptake of Cd is inhibited by the Ca channel blockers. Due to high concentration of Ca around Ca channels, Cd uptake was possibly decreased by competition for metal ion influx. There is a need to get further information about low Ca levels and ion strength that affect the Cd uptake.

Acknowledgement

Authors are grateful to Dr. Alok Lehri, Incharge, CIF Division, National Botanical Research Institute, Lucknow for analyzing soil and plant samples for heavy metals by AAS (Model Perkin-Elmer, Analyst600).

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